

Studies on Oxo-Metal Cations: Dioxo-Molybdenum(VI) Complexes

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Transitional elements of Group IV, V and VI are known to form mononuclear oxo-cations of the type MO^{+n} and MO_2^{+n} . The most thoroughly investigated, best characterised and most stable oxo-metal entities are the dioxo-uranium(VI)^{1,2} and oxo-vanadium(IV)³ ions. The next best characterised and most studied oxo-cation is the oxo-molybdenum ion⁴. The strongly bound oxygens of these oxo-metal cations remain intact during chemical reactions and produce one or more additional absorption bands beyond those normally available with transition metal complexes. With a view to have a wide variety of oxo-metal cations and to study their chemistry, we have described a large number of oxo-vanadium (IV & V) and dioxo-uranium (VI) complexes⁵⁻⁸. It has now been possible to extend the vistas of such studies to dioxo-molybdenum(VI) or molybdenyl ion, MoO_2^{+2} .

Coordination complexes of hexavalent molybdenum are very little known⁹. The ligands which have been found to form complexes with Mo(VI) are oxine¹⁰, acetylacetone^{10,11,12}, benzoylphenylhydroxylamine¹³, aminoacids¹⁴, EDTA¹⁵, tropolone¹⁶, oxine-5-sulphonic acid¹⁴, oxalic acid¹⁰, hydroxamic acids¹⁷, dimethylsulphoxide¹⁸, triphenylphosphin oxide¹⁸, triphenylarsin oxide¹², Schiff bases¹⁹ etc. of the various ligands that have been investigated, acetylacetone has received major attention^{10,11}. Though the dioxo-molybdenum(VI) complexes with β -diketones are well established,

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nothing has appeared so far in the literature concerning Mo(VI) complexes with some other oxygen donors, viz., acetoacetanilides, benzoylacetanilides, salicylanilides and closely related koziic acid. This note relates to the synthesis and characterisation of such complexes.

General method of synthesis of Mo(VI) complexes: Ammonium molybdate tetrahydrate (1 mole) was dissolved in minimum amount of 6*N* HCl. The appropriate ligand (2 mole) was dissolved in minimum amount of ethanol. These two solutions were then mixed and *pH* of the mixture was adjusted to 2 with 6*N* HCl. The yellow solution formed was evaporated on a steam bath to about half the original volume. Yellow crystalline products separated on cooling were filtered off, washed with ethanol and dried in a desiccator. In some cases where an oil was formed, crystalline products were obtained by scratching the oily mass with ethanol. In case of koziic acid, the ligand was dissolved in water and there was instantaneous precipitation after adjustment of *pH*. All these complexes are soluble in methanol, ethanol and insoluble in water.

TABLE I

Oxo-molybdenum (VI) Complexes

Complex	Colour	Analytical	results		Molar conductance mhos	Decomposition temp. °C
			%Mo	%N		
bis-Acetoacetanilido-dioxo-Mo (VI) [MoO ₂ (C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂ N) ₂]	Yellow	Found Reqd:	20.2 20.2	5.7 5.8	10	195
bis-Benzoylacetanilido-dioxo-Mo(VI) [MoO ₂ (C ₁₃ H ₁₂ O ₂ N) ₂]	Orange yellow	Found: Reqd:	16.0 15.9	4.8 4.6	6	234
bis-Benzoyl-meta-nitroacetanilido-dioxo-Mo (VI) [MoO ₂ (C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₂) ₂]	Yellow	Found: Reqd:	14.1 13.8	7.8 8.0	5	237
bis-Salicylanilido-dioxo-Mo(VI) [MoO ₂ (C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₂ N) ₂]	Yellow	Found: Read:	17.1 17.3	5.1 5.0	6	255
bis-Kozato-dioxo-Mo (VI) [MoO ₂ (C ₆ H ₅ O ₄) ₂]	Pale yellow	Found: Reqd:	23.4 23.4	—	7	215

On the basis of analytical data the general molecular formula can be represented as [MoO₂L₂] (where LH=acetoacetanilide, benzoylacetanilide, salicylanilide or koziic acid), showing that only two molecules of chelating ligands are coordinated per molybdenum atom and molybdenum is hexa-coordinated. The complexes are very stable and do not decompose on heating at 120° for hours. The electrolytic conductance measurements in methanol solution were carried out with the help of a Philip's Conductivity Bridge and a dip type cell. Low molar conductance values ($\Lambda_M=5-10$ mhos) are indicative of non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. The complexes are extractable by immiscible higher alcohols around *pH* 2.5, showing that the compounds remain practically undissociated

and non-electrolyte around this low pH region. The room temperature magnetic moments were determined by the Gouy method with solid specimens. All the complexes were found to be diamagnetic as expected for a $4d^0$ system and no major difference between the magnetic properties of the molybdenyl ions was noticed in these complexes. The electronic absorption spectra in ethanol solution were recorded with the help of a Hilger-Watts Uvispeck Spectrophotometer using one cm. cells. The spectra reveal that all the complexes are transparent in the 330-800 $m\mu$ region. Only a charge transfer type of band was noticed in the ultraviolet region. This observation is in line with other molybdenum(VI) complexes^{12,17}. The ethanolic solutions of the complexes did not fluoresce in ultraviolet light at room temperature.

The persistence of the molybdenum-oxygen bond in all these complexes may be considered to be established from the infra red spectra of the complexes. The infra red spectra of the complexes, as for the other molybdenum(VI) complexes,¹⁰⁻¹⁹ exhibit a strong molybdenyl band around 910-920 cm^{-1} . The corresponding band in *bis* acetyl acetonato dioxo-molybdenum(VI) is located¹⁰ at 905 cm^{-1} . The band position is truly indicative of a $O=Mo=O$ species rather than $Mo=O$, as oxo-metal cation involving a single oxygen metal multiple covalent bond absorbs at considerably higher frequency region^{4,20} around 970-980 cm^{-1} .

In Table 1 the complexes are a typical representative of a series of substituted acetoacetanilides, benzoylacetanilides and salicylanilides, which are now being studied. Action of a large number of bidentate ligands(both oxygen and nitrogen donors) on $(NH_4)_6 Mo_7 O_{24} \cdot 4H_2O$ and also on MoO_2Cl_2 are in progress. Studies on the thermal dissociation of these complexes and also of $[MoO_2(acac)_2]$ are under investigation and details will be published in due course. Reactions of these ligands with other oxidation states of Mo are progressing.

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